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The student as a customer in higher education: a systematic review (2000–2022)

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ABSTRACT

The metaphor of the student as customer has long generated controversy among authors due to its commercial background based on the payment that students make for their education. This situation positions them as customers of the university and as consumers of their education. Despite numerous investigations, no studies have yet conducted a systematic review of the literature based on the antagonistic positions (negative and positive).

The aim of this study lies precisely in filling this gap by investigating works written from 2000 to 2022, to retrospectively analyze the arguments both for and against the metaphor. To achieve this, a systematic review was conducted in Scopus and Web of Science databases following the procedures of the Prisma Statement. After applying the selection criteria, 83 studies were identified.

The findings revealed that the proposed thematic axes correspond to the two main stances presented by the researchers, allowing for a two-dimensional categorization based on negative and positive perspectives on the subject. In addition, it was evidenced that the authors develop their arguments across various contexts.

This study aims to set aside conventional paradigms and contribute to broadening the knowledge of the problem, transparently channeling the critical analysis of the subject.

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1. Introduction

Universities, over the years, have been influenced by various theories such as neoliberalism (Mintz, 2021), marketisation (Judson & Taylor, 2014; Nixon et al., 2018), Total Quality Management (TQM) (Eagle & Brennan, 2007), commodification (Saunders & Blanco Ramirez, 2017), to mention a few. Such theories have driven a philosophical shift in the way higher education unfolds, to achieve instrumental and not necessarily academic goals (Budd, 2017; Vuori, 2013). The most relevant principle has been marketisation, which proposes that education should be oriented towards the achievement of marketing objectives (Furedi, 2010). It is precisely on this theoretical framework that the student as customer metaphor is based, whose essence, centered on business models and educational marketing, generates controversy among authors, by promoting a customer-oriented culture/mindset to ensure satisfactory services to students (Ma, 2020; Pitman, 2016).

Taking this concept as a premise, researchers have been investigating the student as customer with mixed research techniques and addressing different topics, for example: service quality in higher education (Calma & Dickson-Deane, 2020), experience and satisfaction (Thien & Jamil, 2020), academic performance and educational outcomes (Bunce et al., 2017; Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2009), student customer experience (Dropulić et al., 2021), co-creation and co-production behaviors (Tari Kasnaoğlu & Mercan, 2022; McCulloch, 2009), service logic (Ng & Forbes, 2009), administrative service quality (Steppacher et al., 2021), personal branding (Parrott, 2019), student perceptions (Tomlinson, 2017), student identity

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(Zainol et al., 2019), faculty-student relationship (Lomas, 2007), faculty commitment (Xiao & Wilkins, 2015), across different academic programs (Xu et al., 2018), in different countries (Budd, 2017; Serenko, 2011), or according to students' ages and gender (Finney & Finney, 2010), student loyalty (Mulyono et al., 2020), protection and legal perspective (Brooks, 2022; Zhou, 2020), among others.

Similarly, the literature also reveals presence of other metaphors that describe the various roles that students assume during their educational experience (Serenko, 2011), such as: consumers (Bunce et al., 2017), employees (Gillespie & Parry, 2009; Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2009), partners (Clayson & Haley, 2005), citizens (Cuthbert, 2010), pawns, apprentices (Tight, 2013), professional - client relationship (Bailey, 2000), among other designations.

At this point, it is important to note that various authors who have researched on the student as a customer across diverse contexts and topics have permanently expressed their polarized views, either in favor of or against the issue (Redding, 2005). Its representatives and advocates embrace the metaphor, arguing that it allows empowering students and, moreover, enables education to focus on achieving quality teaching with accomplishment and satisfaction indicators (Guilbault, 2016; McCulloch, 2009; Ng & Forbes, 2009). Critics of the metaphor, however, argue that universities become commodities where contractual relationships are harbored, as students perceive education as a product that can be acquired based on their demands (Bay & Daniel, 2001; Brennan & Bennington, 2000; Bunce et al., 2017; Molesworth et al., 2009). Other authors, in turn, have suggested that this perspective is too narrow and that considering the student as customer and as a co-producer, better frames the role of young individuals as managers of their own education, thereby creating value and promoting a shared responsibility between students and the university (Cao et al., 2019; Mark, 2013).

However, despite the numerous investigations and the discrepancy of opinions among experts, there is no research that has structured a literature review from the antagonistic positions of the authors. The aim of this research is to fill this gap by achieving the following objectives: First, to conduct a review of the literature on the student as a customer over a 22-year period (from 2000 to 2022). Second, to identify and retrospectively analyze authors' pro- and con- positions regarding the student as customer metaphor. Third, to propose a categorization of the literature based on a dichotomy of opinions, considering the different topics studied by researchers regarding the issue. Consequently, this review aims to ensure that those interested do not remain with a biased view on the topic, but rather to understand the existing positions and be able to form an informed opinion.

To achieve this, the present article has applied a methodological design based on the procedures for conducting systematic reviews proposed by Kitchenham (2004). Additionally, to ensure the quality of the research, the Prisma Statement (González de Dios et al., 2011) was used as a guiding framework. To execute these procedures, two research questions were formulated: (1) What are the negative stances towards the student as customer metaphor? (2) What are the positive orientations towards the student as customer metaphor? As will be explained in detail in the methodological section, a research strategy with keywords was employed in two recognized databases such as Scopus and the Web of Science, given their extensive coverage of high-quality journals and significant impact (Dropulić et al., 2021; Kacprzak & Hensel, 2023). Subsequently, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, a flowchart with the phases of the study selection process was developed and the results with a comparative table of the authors' positions were presented. Finally, the conclusions, the limitations and the suggestions for future studies were proposed.

The research contributes to both the fields of marketing and education, offering an original and updated source of information to cease from labeling a priori students - customers as either beneficial - harmful (Ma, 2020), and to transparently guide the critical analysis on the subject from the contributions of this research.

2. Methodology

To analyze the published literature on the student as a customer in higher education, a systematic review was carried out according to the procedures proposed by Kitchenham (2004), which include the following phases:

- Planning the review, which involves defining research questions and developing a search strategy to identify keywords, to delimit the most relevant sources of information or databases according to the disciplinary field.

- Conducting the review, which includes the specification of inclusion/exclusion criteria, data extraction and article selection.
- Reporting the review, which requires the presentation and discussion of the results.

Similarly, to ensure the quality of the review, the items of the Prisma Statement (González de Dios et al., 2011) corresponding to the verification of systematics reviews were also considered:

- Title and abstract, indicating that it is a systematic review and preparing a structured summary.
- Introduction, detailing the justification of the topic and the objectives, explicitly stating the research questions.
- Method, presenting the characteristics of the search, sources of information, eligibility criteria, selection of studies and data extraction.
- Results, disclosing the selection of studies and possible biases.
- Discussion, considering the main findings, the limitations of the results and the conclusions.
- Flow chart showing the phases of the systematic review.

The objective is to carry out a systematic review of the literature, identifying the currents around study (Codina, 2018); in this case, it is about identifying the negative and positive currents regarding the student as customer metaphor.

2.1. Research questions and literature search

For this purpose, two thematic axes were traced from the research questions: (1) Negative currents towards the student as customer metaphor; (2) Positive currents towards the student as customer metaphor. Table 1 shows the research questions.

Secondly, the identification of the universe of published articles was carried out by conducting out a search between 10 October 2022, and 10 March 2023, in the two main international editorial catalogs, namely Scopus and the Web of Science. The search was conducted based on the total or partial appearance of the following keywords (Arnau-Sabatés & Sala Roca, 2020), either in the title or in the abstracts of the works: 'student as customer' and 'higher education', 'student as consumer' and 'higher education', 'student as client' and 'higher education', 'estudiante cliente' and 'educación superior'. As can be deduced, the keywords have used search commands in both English and Spanish, and, therefore, studies have been selected only in these languages, this statement will be explained below.

2.2. Selection criteria for the study

Firstly, the research was limited to publications between 2000 and 2022 because, starting in the new millennium, the massification of higher education showed a vertiginous acceleration, increasing between 2000 and 2018 by 18.96% (Ezcurra, 2020). This situation led to greater competition among educational institutions to attract students with differential benefits (Ma, 2020), which made the conception of the student as customer become more prominent and, therefore, a topic of interest to research from then on.

Another inclusion criterion was the consideration of works that addressed disciplines such as education, marketing, economics, administration, among others, and were developed using any research method.

Likewise, the review included publications in English and Spanish; regarding the English language, it was observed that publications related to the topic of study have been written in that language, crossing borders. This is how studies from the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, America, Asia and Europe are contemplated in this investigation. Likewise, publications in

Table 1. Guiding research questions for the study.

ID	Research questions (RQ)
RQ1	What are the negative stances towards the student as customer metaphor?
RQ2	What are the positive orientations towards the student as customer metaphor?

Source: own elaboration.

Table 2. Criteria for inclusion and exclusion of works within the universe.

ID	Category	Criteria
IN1	Inclusion	Articles published between 2000 and 2022 in English and Spanish
IN2	Inclusion	Articles referring to research questions
IN3	Inclusion	Articles developed with any research method and in various disciplines
EX1	Exclusion	Articles with a specialized focus on other topics
EX2	Exclusion	Articles focused on graduate students

Source: own elaboration.

Spanish have been considered because the research is carried out in an Ibero-American country and Spain has interesting contributions from researchers on the problem.

It is also important to mention that the study established inclusion criteria around the subject matter to be addressed (Barredo-Ibáñez et al., 2021). Thus, the selected works had to focus on the student as customer metaphor in undergraduate higher education and the negative and positive currents of thought surrounding this metaphor. In this way, the conceptual framework was defined and the organization of knowledge about the discipline under study was determined (Hart, 2018).

It is pertinent to mention that research with a specialized focus on other topics was excluded, such as, for example: strictly pedagogical articles, tuition fees and university reforms, student mobility, meta learning metrics, legal matters, dancing and music techniques, brand image and reputation, or public health sustainability, etc. Finally, it is worth mentioning that research with graduate students was excluded, since they have a very different profile and the studies carried out are not framed around the metaphor of the student as a customer, but rather on investigating their satisfaction considering their advanced degree. Table 2 below shows the criteria.

2.3. Study selection

After reading the titles and abstracts of the 281 documents located in the Scopus and Web of Science databases, their relevance was discussed through the formation of a nominal group (Guillen Zanón, 1990) comprised of the three authors of this study. Two stages were followed for this purpose: the first, focused on the decision to exclude works by consensus; and the second, focused on discussing discrepancies arising from the selection of works. Following this process and considering the inclusion criteria, 127 studies were selected. Then, considering the exclusion criteria and some duplicate articles, 49 works were discarded. The application of these filters resulted in a total of 78 works. Finally, following the procedure developed by Matus et al. (2021), 5 articles were included in the universe that were referenced by some of the cited authors, despite not meeting the search criteria and that were found through Google Scholar. Taking this into consideration, 83 works were the final sample that met the inclusion criteria. Figure 1 shows the search and selection process flow.

Following the steps proposed by Codina (2018), the texts of the 83 works were downloaded, verified to meet quality standards, and then analyzed. Initially, the works were classified according to defined thematic axes (positions for and against the student as customer metaphor). Each author was then responsible for analyzing and producing critical synthesis of an assigned group of works. The lead author then systematized the contributions with successive interactions from the other authors until the common ground between the documents was defined. Finally, at least two joint reviews by all authors were considered to integrate the contributions.

2.4. Data synthesis

Below is an analysis that identifies the 83 publications by year of publication, type of document, study method, and geographic location.

2.4.1. Year of publication

The distribution of the 83 documents published over the 22 years shows the most significant growth between 2015 and 2020. This increase may be related to the predominance of empirical studies, which reached 62.5% compared to conceptual studies, which reached 37.5%. These results could imply that, during this period, there was greater production of knowledge based on concrete data (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Phases of the study selection process.
 Source: own elaboration, based on the research.

Figure 2. Distribution of 83 studies grouped by year of publication (2000–2022).
 Source: own elaboration, based on the research.

2.4.2. Document type

After analyzing the document types of the studies reviewed, the documents were classified into journal articles, review articles, conferences papers, book chapters and editorial. Most (93%) correspond to journal articles, as presented in Figure 3.

2.4.3. Study method

After analyzing the 83 selected documents, it was observed that 46% were conceptual studies, 35% employed quantitative methods, 13% were based on qualitative techniques, 3.6% were mixed studies,

Figure 3. Classification of 83 studies by type of document.

Source: own elaboration, based on the research.

and 2.4% were literature reviews. These findings may suggest that a greater empirical contribution characterized this period (2000 – 2022), reaching 51.6% compared to conceptual studies, which reached 46%.

2.4.4. Geographic location

In terms of geographic location, Europe accounts for 36% of the total, with the United Kingdom contributing 25 publications. North America, comprising the United States and Canada, follows with 30%, with the US. leading with 25 works. Asia accounts for 19%, with notable contributions from countries such as Malaysia, China, and Pakistan. Then, there is Oceania with 9.63%, with Australia being the main contributor. Finally, South America and Africa each represent 2.4%. It can be observed that scientific production on the subject is concentrated in the Western world.

Although, as can be inferred from the previous pages, great exhaustiveness has been chosen in the conformation of the universe and in the selection of the sample. It is important to note the limitations of the present systematized review (Araujo Alonso, 2011), such as: (a) the volume of information related to the topics of the present research; (b) possible errors in the search mechanisms; (c) bias in the information (d) access limitations (due to availability); (f) other biases. However, it is worth mentioning that the clear definition of the research questions, the systematization of the contributions with successive interactions of the authors, as well as the reinforcements used through double searches, contributed to minimizing biases and achieving a satisfactory result in the research.

In summary, the process described followed by the systematic analysis of the bibliography has led to the following presented results.

3. Results. Orientation of the student as customer metaphor in higher education

The systematic literature review conducted allows us to determine that the proposed thematic axes respond to the two major currents of opinion (against or in favor) exhibited by the authors regarding the student-as-customer metaphor.

3.1. Positions against the student as customer metaphor

Regarding the first research question related to this negative current, we find Tomlinson (2017), who summarizes the perspectives of researchers who share a position of rejection towards the student as customer metaphor:

When knowledge is reconfigured as a commodity that is bought and exchanged, economic rules related to product (and outcomes) rather than process (related to pedagogy) emerge within higher education institutions. The performance of student as ‘commodity buyers’ and professors as ‘information brokers’, whose role is to package and present the most useful and relevant information in the most efficient way possible, means that fundamental educational values and purposes are significantly marginalized. (p. 4)

For the authors grouped in this assessment, the conceptualization of students as customers is seen as an error that leads to the dehumanization of education under a market logic (Forrest, 2020; Saunders, 2015). This perspective has a negative impact on students' identity, limits their performance and adversely affects academic quality (Furedi, 2010; Ma, 2020; Nixon et al., 2018; Zainol et al., 2019). In this regard, Bunce and Bennett (2021) state that students who consider themselves as customers tend to exhibit low academic performance and may result in passive and instrumental learners (Naidoo et al., 2011).

The vision of the university as a service provider and the student as a customer also implies a decrease in academic rigor (Clayson & Haley, 2005), since young people lack the maturity to determine what is truly beneficial for them. From this perspective, younger individuals often adopt a short-term outlook, believing that grades are the goal rather than an indicator of performance. This mindset may lead them to choose a teacher with low expectations to obtain high grades without exerting much effort. In other words, the literature reviewed points to a significant gap between what students want and what they need (Cuthbert, 2010; Royo, 2017).

Aligned with this perspective, Bay and Daniel (2001) state that students with a customer orientation consider learning as a process of obtaining brief and pre-packaged knowledge, which impairs both the acquisition of higher-level skills and the development of autonomous and permanent learning habits. Consequently, the combination of these factors ends up affecting the participatory role of the educational process (George, 2007). In addition, students consider their education as an investment in their professional future, relying on the belief that effective management of their personal brand will enable them to advance in the labor market (Parrott, 2019; Tomlinson, 2017).

From another perspective, Schwartzman (2017) argues that, in general, it is important to recognize that an undue emphasis on considering the student as a customer, alters the teacher-student relationship, to the point of feeling that, because of the payment, there is a right to demand a treatment according to their preferences, to determine what and how they should be taught, and even to claim or negotiate the grades in evaluations. As Raaper (2019) explains, this perception of students as customers may lead them to expect classes to be entertaining and contain enjoyable information. This would lead students to question and resist the authority of both the teacher and the educational institution. On the other hand, teachers feel that there is a clash between their perceived standards of quality and educational rigor in the education of young people, and the desires of students who, perceiving themselves as customers, seek to complete their subjects quickly and effortlessly, even negotiating their grades (Delucchi & Korgen, 2002; Laing & Laing, 2016; Tomlinson, 2016). This may result in a reduction in the range of disciplinary knowledge and a deterrence of innovation in teaching practices, all which impact on the good public functions of universities (Naidoo & Williams, 2015).

The rise of these principles turns education into an impersonal transaction (Ruth, 2018), a means to achieve immediate and instrumental goals, such as obtaining an academic degree with the aim of securing a good job and high salaries, instead of pursuing long-term intellectual development (Molesworth et al., 2009). This current also appeals to some teachers and academics who strive for positive ratings in student surveys to be recognized for the fulfillment of educational management indicators, rather than for genuine teaching (Page, 2020).

Cuthbert (2010) states that the role of students as customers should be limited to the realm of university services, such as the library, cafeteria, and sports facilities, but not extended to academic activities. In this sense, Saunders (2015) is of the opinion that there should not be a generalized orientation to consider students as customers, because this role could be influenced by factors that are beyond academics. These factors pertain to infrastructure services and the overall experience that students live in higher education institutions (Arboleda & Alonso, 2017).

Regarding the management indicators that universities are implementing, Watjatrakul (2014) states that these practices, which are based on product marketing, should not be directly applied to an educational environment. They argue that these measures are more concrete in business models than they are to reflect achievements in learning (Calma & Dickson-Deane, 2020).

Another issue addressed by the authors is the positive impact of social influence on the intentions of young people when selecting universities that embrace the student as a customer model. They consider that they will have modern services and pleasant environments; however, these same students also

express their concern about the possibility of encountering low academic standards at these institutions (Wajtrakul, 2014).

Based on the arguments presented above, there is evidence of a negative trend among authors who consider the concept of the student as customer as something harmful and detrimental to the academic development of young people. They argue that educational institutions that embrace this principle prioritize commercial interests over the purposes of authentic teaching (Mintz, 2021). Although this perspective reflects genuine concerns, it may overlook the reality that higher education cannot deny the existence of a consumer culture. The challenge lies in not succumbing to it and reminding students that academic achievements are not obtained simply by paying tuition, but through effort, commitment, and desire to excel (Royo, 2017).

3.2. Positions in favor of the student as customer metaphor

Regarding the second research question related to pro-student-as-customer positions, the authors who agree with this approach mention that higher education involves various stakeholders (future employers, the government, and society); however, they point out that the students are the primary customers of educational institutions, as they are the reason for their existence (Guilbault, 2016). Placing the student as a customer at the center of decision-making helps democratize educational experience and contributes to improving the quality of higher education (Maringe, 2010).

The researchers who support the student as customer model are based on the concept of co-production. According to McCulloch (2009), the definition of co-production that best suits the 21st-century higher education is the one proposed by Bovaird (2007) which refers to 'the provision of services through long-term relationships between providers and users, where both parties make a substantial contribution of resources' (p. 847). The idea is that clients should be actively involved and play a participatory role, working together with the company to complete the service offering satisfactorily (Bateson, 2002; Lengnick-Hall et al., 2000; Torkzadeh et al., 2021).

In the educational context, co-production would imply a more comprehensive and meaningful commitment to ensure quality and enhance learning (Dollinger et al., 2018; Little & Williams, 2010). In that way, this is a process that would entail a greater dialogue of students with institutions, with their teachers and peers, adopting an approach of active contributors to pedagogical processes, rather than simply being recipients of educational services (Carter & Yeo, 2016; Judson & Taylor, 2014; Tomlinson, 2016).

In this sense, Eagle and Brennan (2007) affirm that the concept of customer involvement derives from the service marketing literature and implies more complex conceptions as education is an intangible service that involves the customer in the production process and is provided over a period. In other words, higher education is an experiential service focused on the experience that the student has with the organization, which goes far beyond considering only the provision of benefits. Students participate in higher education not to buy an experience, but rather to explore, co-create and be co-responsible for it. Therefore, the student as customer is not reduced to a product, as they are conceived as active participants willing to be challenged in the educational process (Finney & Finney, 2010; Pitman, 2016; Tight, 2013). It is precisely these inclusive and innovative practices that transform university life and reflect the diversity of its participants (Partington, 2020).

The criticisms of the student as customer model appear to be based on an outdated marketing perspective; 'the customer is always right' (Guilbault, 2018; Ip et al., 2017). However, there have been significant advances in theory, to the point where in numerous institutions, student customers are no longer seen as passive recipients, but as active participants in their education with wide and varied expectations of the university, such as obtaining their academic degree or the desire for motivating classroom sessions (Budd, 2017; Xu et al., 2018).

It is pertinent to note that the role of higher education institutions is not to satisfy the needs and desires of students, but to provide them with the resources to actively participate in the activities required for their learning (Ng & Forbes, 2009). Under this principle, teachers are seen as coaches, value managers, or instructors who offer their expert knowledge and abilities to educate. However, it is the students who must contribute to the management of their learning, and assuming a series of tasks to achieve their educational goals (Díaz-Méndez et al., 2019; Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2009; Kotzé & Plessis, 2003).

At this point, it is worth noting that shared responsibility or co-production among the various participants in the educational activity has shown positive effects on the attitudinal, emotional, and behavioral responses to the educational experience, creating value for students, teachers, and the university (Cao et al., 2019; Mark, 2013; Sierra, 2010). The mentioned accountability has also been beneficial in terms of feedback received by students to enhance educational processes and quality (Xu et al., 2018). Similarly, Tari Kasnakoğlu and Mercan (2022) emphasize the importance of co-creation to generate reciprocal interrelationships between educators and students to achieve positive gains in higher education.

On the other hand, it has been observed in the analysis of the literature studied that, although some authors are against the student as customer model, they support the student's co-producer profile (Calma & Dickson-Deane, 2020) but dissociate it from the concept of a customer. On the opposite side, there are authors who see education as the result of the co-creation and co-production of a service (Torkzadeh et al., 2021) and, therefore, establish an association between the student as customer and the participatory role they play in their training.

Considering a more institutional vision and due to the need for differentiation in the educational sector, some authors argue that universities have developed management indicators to promote efficiency and effectiveness in their performance. These indicators include enrollment rates, retention rates, placements in international rankings, satisfaction levels, quality standards in services and infrastructure, among other aspects (Elsharnouby, 2015; Lomas, 2007; Steppacher et al., 2021; Woodall et al., 2014). It is through the communication of these attributes that universities achieve a reputation as respectable institutions, which facilitates the attraction of new students (Cardoso et al., 2011; Raza et al., 2021), the retention of current students, and enables them to capture the attention of corporate entities for agreements and research funding (Budd, 2017; Govender et al., 2022).

Another aspect to consider in this stance is the need of employing multi-criteria segmentation (Khusnuliawati & Putri, 2021) to define marketing strategies capable of addressing the variation in students' demographic, psychographic and behavioral characteristics. These criteria align with the principle of treating customers as individuals, a trend that emerged as a dominant force in defining the educational market (Smith & Haub, 2013). Similarly, categorizing clients into profitable, long-term, or good clients is another business trend being implemented in higher education institutions (Harrison-Walker, 2010).

Researchers claim that the new generation of student customers has become increasingly selective when choosing universities (Xiao & Wilkins, 2015). According to the authors cited, students will primarily select an educational institution if it has adequate mobile technology and digital resources (Ali et al., 2018; Raza et al., 2018), if the quality and learning environment are satisfactory, and if its image is friendly and compatible with them (Ho & Law, 2022; Ip et al., 2017; Redding, 2005).

Another important aspect to consider is the educational experience (Muncy, 2008). In this regard, the research by Koris and Nokelainen (2015) delves into the topic to identify whether students expect to be treated as customers or not, based on the different aspects of their educational experience. This research broke the paradigm suggesting that students who considered themselves as customers were not interested in relevant aspects of their education. Instead, it allowed visualizing them as young individuals genuinely concerned about their academic development, as described by Guilbault (2016).

According to the arguments presented, it is evident that the authors aligned with this positive position consider that the concept of the student as customer is beneficial. They believe it rescues the participatory and co-productive role of young individuals and, in addition, facilitates the implementation of institutional mechanisms necessary to ensure the quality of education and satisfaction. However, it is crucial to not lose sight of the fact that the main mission of universities is to educate and train future professionals who serve the community rather than to satisfy corporate agendas and demands (Eagle & Brennan, 2007).

Finally, considering that the systematic literature review determined that the proposed thematic axes, based on the research questions, respond to the two major currents of opinion (for and against) displayed by the authors regarding the student as customer metaphor; Table 3, presents a categorization of the literature based on this dichotomy of opinion, taking into account the main topics and arguments addressed regarding the study issue.

Table 3. Positions against and in favor of the student as customer metaphor: studies located and key arguments.

Principal topics	Student - Customer / positions against		Student - Customer / positions in favor	
	Studies located	Key arguments	Studies located	Key arguments
The role of the student as customer	Cuthbert, 2010; Serenko, 2011, Svensson & Wood, 2007;	The role of the student and customer are incompatible and should only be placed in the realm of university services, but not in academic activities.	Finney & Finney, 2010; Little & Williams, 2010; Maringe, 2010; Pitman, 2016; Tight, 2013; Xu et al., 2018; Vuori, 2013.	Centering decisions around the student as a customer helps with the democratization of educational experience. The student is an active contributor and willing to be challenged in the educational process.
The value of higher education	Forrest, 2020; Ma, 2020; Mintz, 2021; Saunders, 2015; Zainol et al., 2019.	The conceptualization of the student as a customer implicitly reflects the acceptance of the marketisation and dehumanization of higher education.	Banwait & Hancock, 2021; Cao et al., 2019; Dollinger et al., 2018; Judson & Taylor, 2014; Mark, 2013; Sierra, 2010; Tari Kasnakoğlu & Mercan, 2022; Torkzadeh et al., 2021.	Shared responsibility and co-production have demonstrated positive effects, creating value between students and the university. Maintaining long-term sustainable student value is a priority.
The role of universities	Bay & Daniel, 2001; Brennan & Bennington, 2000; Bunce et al., 2017; Ma, 2020; Molesworth et al., 2009; Page, 2020; Saunders & Blanco, 2017.	With marketisation, universities become commodities where contractual relationships are harbored, and education is seen as a product that can be acquired.	Dropulić et al., 2021; Eagle & Brennan, 2007; Lengnick-Hall et al., 2000; Partington, 2020; Raza et al., 2021, Steppacher et al., 2021	The role of universities is to provide the necessary resources (infrastructure, technology, services) for students to become actively involved in their education as agents of change and future workforce of the industry.
Academic rigor	Bailey, 2000; Clayson & Haley, 2005; Furedi, 2010; George, 2007; Naidoo et al., 2011; Nixon et al., 2018.	The role of the student as a customer decreases academic rigor. Learning becomes pre-packaged knowledge, affecting students' performance and participatory role.	Guilbault, 2016; Koris & Nokelainen, 2015; McCulloch, 2009; Ng & Forbes, 2009.	Students as customers seek rigor and academic demand. In addition, by empowering them, a quality approach to teaching with indicators of achievement and satisfaction is generated.
Teacher -student relationship	Delucchi & Korgen, 2002; Laing & Laing, 2016; Naidoo & Williams, 2015; Tomlinson, 2016; Raaper, 2019; Schwartzman, 2017.	The student-teacher relationship undergoes significant changes due to the payment made. The student demands what should be taught, seeks to negotiate their grades, and aims to pass their subjects quickly.	Díaz - Méndez et al., 2019; Kotzé & Plessis, 2003; McCulloch, 2009	Teachers are coaches and students should contribute to the management of their learning by co-producing and assuming tasks and responsibilities.
Demands - Satisfaction	Bunce & Bennett, 2021; Cuthbert, 2010; Royo, 2017.	Students question the teacher's authority. They have insufficient interest in learning. There is a gap between what they want and what they need in terms of educational training.	Carter & Yeo, 2016; Ng & Forbes, 2009; Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2009; Govender et al., 2022; Guilbault, 2018:	The co-production of learning takes place between teachers, students, and administrative staff, resulting in a satisfying academic experience where the student strives for achievements and goals.
Educational Orientation	Molesworth et al., 2009; Parrot, 2019; Ruth, 2018; Tomlinson, 2017.	Education is perceived as an investment for a professional future, to achieve instrumental and immediate goals such as acquiring an academic degree.	Ali et al., 2018; Budd, 2017; Ho & Law, 2022; Ip et al., 2017; Mulyono et al., 2020; Muncy, 2008; Raza et al., 2018; Redding, 2005; Xiao & Wilkins, 2015.	Students have become very selective when choosing educational institutions considering technology, digital resources, degrees, prestige, services, and motivating classes.
Business focus and higher education	Calma & Dickson-Deane, 2020; Watjatrakul, 2014.	Using management principles or indicators in the educational field implies losing the academic focus on profitability based on revenue generation, which does not reflect the achievements of the learning process.	Arboleda & Alonso, 2017; Elsharnouby, 2015; Gillespie & Parry, 2009; Harrison-Walker, 2010; Lomas, 2007; Smith & Haub, 2013; Thien & Jamil, 2020; Woodall et al., 2014; Khusnuliawati & Putri, 2021.	It is beneficial to adopt business principles to provide a satisfactory educational experience to students at both academic and service levels. Good teaching, clear goals and standards, provides student satisfaction.

Source: own elaboration, based on the research.

4. Conclusions

Nowadays, higher education institutions operate in a dynamic environment of intense competition where funding follows student choice (Banwait & Hancock, 2021). Given that the marketisation approach implies the commercialization of education (Furedi, 2010), it is logical to think that students are increasingly taking on the role of customers in their relationship with universities (Koris & Nokelainen, 2015). This has led to a greater customer orientation among universities adopting a tendency to serve rather than challenge students to achieve academic goals through a better educational experience (Svensson & Wood, 2007). However, the debate is polarized, and controversy is a characteristic that has been evident in the research carried out on the subject (Guilbault, 2018).

This investigation has allowed us to delve deeper into this debate and identify, based on the research questions, the presence of the two thematic axes in the authors' works: positions in favor and positions against the student as customer metaphor in the period from 2000 to 2022. To date, an analytical approach that identifies, evaluates, and classifies these antagonistic points of view following an exhaustive research process such as a systematic literature review has not been developed. The purpose of this study is precisely to fill this gap.

In reference to the first research question, related to the negative positions towards the student as customer metaphor, it was observed that the authors expressed their negativity and rejection because they considered the marketization of education as a harmful theory that prevented satisfactory educational development (Calma & Dickson-Deane, 2020). Opposition to the concept was manifested on several fronts, such as lack of interest in learning, academic underperformance, a short-term and easy vision focused on the academic degree, resistance to the professor's authority, demand for entertaining classes, good grades with little effort, determining teaching content, demand high-quality academic services, management indicators oriented to business achievements, among others (Molesworth et al., 2009).

The mindset embraced by this approach is: 'the customer, because they pay, is right and their demands must be satisfied'. This marketing principle has evolved substantially and, moreover, this judgment is not applicable to education, since it is not a product, but an experiential service. In other words, students want to belong to a university not to buy education, but to explore and co-create the educational experience, with the aim of gestate learning throughout this process with the guidance of their instructors. To consider that the student does not possess a genuine desire to learn by assuming a customer role and to assert that universities are focused only on satisfying their demands by easily granting academic degrees, are conceptions based on an outdated notion of customer subservience (Guilbault, 2016).

Regarding the second question, which explored the positive orientations towards the student as customer metaphor, authors were identified as an optimistic stance regarding the concept, considering that the commodification of education has stimulated a proposal for constant differentiation and innovation in the provision of educational services by universities (Mulyono et al., 2020). From this perspective, acceptance of the concept is evidenced in statements such as: the student as customer is a co-producer and not a receptive consumer of education, the objective of satisfaction is to provide students with the necessary resources for optimal learning, teachers are mentors who accompany their training, it is genuine to show interest in obtaining an academic degree, it is beneficial for universities to have management indicators to guarantee educational quality, among other arguments (Díaz - Méndez et al., 2019).

This perspective emphasizes that students as customers are primarily interested in learning and in enhancing their academic training and, while also being aware that if they do not develop in a co-productive role, they will not achieve their academic goals. Similarly, authors value the presence of educational marketing within the corporate management of universities, since it allows the construction of a service chain that adequately meets students' needs, providing the resources for a satisfactory educational experience (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2000) The problem arises when this perspective is oriented more towards economic goals rather than educational ones.

On the other hand, regarding the sample, it is worth highlighting that research on the student as customer metaphor was dominated by empirical studies (51.6%), which intensified starting in 2015. This may be because, in the first decade of the 2000s, studies on the issue focused on conceptual research (46%), followed by the need for empirical evidence from concrete data. With respect to geographic location, Europe and North America lead the scientific production on the topic, with Great Britain and the

United States in first place with 25 works each. Although other countries such as China, Australia, Pakistan, and Malaysia have researched the issue, it is observed that the predominance is in the Western world. This may be because neoliberal currents (Mintz, 2021) and marketisation principles (Nixon et al., 2018) emerged in Europe and North America respectively, since the previous century. These currents of thought have influenced the orientation of higher education institutions toward instrumental rather than academic achievements (Banwait & Hancock, 2021). Therefore, it is likely that scientific interest in the subject has been highlighted in these regions.

In reference to the theoretical and practical implications, the theoretical implication provided by this study lies in proposing a two-dimensional categorization of the literature, considering the discordant positions of the authors, in order to contribute with an updated source of information that proposes a critical analysis so that those interested in the subject are not influenced a priori by the student customer paradigm, associating it only with something beneficial or detrimental (Ma, 2020), but can elaborate their opinion based on the contributions of this review. At the practical level, this study allows different stakeholders to understand the factors underlying student customer orientations, both positive and negative, so they can make better decisions. In this sense, according to the findings, university managers should better understand student customer expectations and not neglect academic quality in the interest of improving functional services and profitability. Faculty could encourage co-production as part of their teaching methodology and stop considering the student customer as unrelated to their academic interests. Parents could guide their children on the proper balance they should maintain as students and as customers to achieve their academic goals. Students could better identify the academic or business options offered by higher education institutions and choose the one that best suits their professional development goals.

In summary, it is important to mention that, regardless of the controversy, surrounding the concept of the student as a customer, the challenge lies in educational institutions providing the necessary services with high standards, while ensuring that students develop their educational competencies by fulfilling their responsibilities and duties (Dropulić et al., 2021, pp. 221).

4.1. Limitations and future investigation

Regarding limitations, it is important to mention that to develop this review, the sources were in English and Spanish, and it is likely that relevant works on the topic exist in other languages, which would have been valuable to consider. Likewise, some articles were found that, while tangentially related to the topic of the student as a customer, their primary focus encompassed other topics. Similarly, the literature review identified some gaps in the topic that could inspire future research. First, since there has been little in-depth knowledge of the various aspects underlying students as customers' behavior, it is suggested that research be conducted that considers their sociocultural environment, demographic variables, academic programs, educational preferences, among other aspects, in order to discover the factors that could help determine a typology or classification that contributes to better profiling them. Secondly, it can be noted that the approach to the problem has recurrently centered on the student, while the metaphor has been conceived because of changes in the way education has been organized and financed. In other words, the situation has not been instigated by student initiative but by the conflict between the academia and the corporate university management. It would be valuable to further investigate this collision with a neutral view towards the student. Finally, since studies on the problem have not considered in depth the perspective of other stakeholders, it is suggested to comparatively investigate the arguments of the different actors involved, such as students' parents, teachers, employers, academic authorities, administrative staff, media, among others. Knowing these insights and contrasting them would provide new perspectives into the phenomenon.

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Ethical approval

The approval of an ethics committee was not required because the information included in the research does not correspond to sensitive personal data. The survey was administered with the consent of the respondents and was anonymous.

Authors' contribution

Zarela Goyzueta conceived and planned the investigation. Zarela Goyzueta developed the theory and proposed the methodology under the supervision of Daniel Barredo and Carolina Consolación - Segura. Daniel Barredo encouraged Zarela Goyzueta to investigate possible positions of the authors on the topic of study. All authors supervised the findings of this work and discussed the results. Zarela Goyzueta wrote the manuscript with input from all authors.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available on scopus.com and webofscience.com. The derived data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author on request.

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